

Borate complexes in solution. Part-II. Complex formation equilibria of some *cis*-diaqua-Co^{III} complexes with boric acid^ψ

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Potentiometric studies on the complex formation equilibria of *cis*-diaqua-Co^{III} complexes of the type, *cis*-[(N₄)Co(H₂O)₂]³⁺, where, N₄ represents one mole of a tetradentate *N*-donor ligand, viz. 1,4,7,10-tetraazadecane (trien) or two moles of a bidentate *N*-donor ligand, viz. 1,3-diaminopropane (tn), 2,2'-bipyridine (bipy), with boric acid (H₃BO₃) in different molar ratios of [(N₄)Co(H₂O)₂]³⁺ : H₃BO₃ in aqueous solution reveal the formation of mononuclear [(N₄)Co(H₂BO₄)] and binuclear [(N₄)Co(BO₄)Co(N₄)]⁺ complexes. Formation constants of the complexes at 25° and at a constant ionic strength of *I* = 0.5 M (NaClO₄) and the complex formation equilibria have been elucidated. The binuclear complexes are found to be predominantly formed over the mononuclear ones. Stability constants of the Co^{III}-borate complexes could be correlated with the p*K*^H values of the *cis*-[(N₄)Co(H₂O)₂]³⁺ ions.

It is well known that acidity of boric acid increases due to its chelate formation with *cis*-1,2-diols, *cis*-2-hydroxy acids and *cis*-1,2-dicarboxylic acids¹. Transition metal complexes having two coordinated OH groups or two H₂O ligands in *cis*-positions are structurally compatible to form analogous chelated structures with boric acid. Although a large number of *cis*-diaqua and *cis*-dihydroxo complexes of different transition metals are well known, till date there is no report of any systematic equilibrium study on the complex formation of such complexes with boric acid in solution. The present paper describes the results of an equilibrium study on the complex formation of boric acid with *cis*-diaquacobalt complexes of the type, *cis*-[(N₄)Co(H₂O)₂]³⁺, where, N₄ represents one mole of a tetradentate *N*-donor ligand, viz. 1,4,7,10-tetraazadecane (trien) or two moles of a bidentate *N*-donor ligand, viz. 1,3-diaminopropane (tn), 2,2'-bipyridine (bipy) by potentiometric method in aqueous solution at 25° and at a constant ionic strength of *I* = 0.5 M (NaClO₄). The results indicate the predominant formation of binuclear mixed ligand borate complexes, [(N₄)Co(BO₄)Co(N₄)]⁺, over the mononuclear [(N₄)Co(H₂BO₄)] complexes.

Results and Discussion

Boric acid (H₃BO₃) acts as a weak monobasic Bronsted acid in the pH range 7.5–9.5 (curve 2, Fig. 1) due to its ionisation, not as a proton donor, but as an OH⁻ acceptor² according to

Fig. 1. Representative pH-titration curves of [Co(trien)(H₂O)₂]³⁺-H₃BO₃ system in aqueous solution, *I* = 0.5 M (NaClO₄), temp. = 25° : (1), 0.002 M HClO₄; (2), (1) + 0.002 M H₃BO₃; (3), (1) + 0.002 M [(trien)Co(H₂O)₂](ClO₄)₃; (4), (3) + 0.002 M H₃BO₃; (5), (1) + 0.004 M [(trien)Co(H₂O)₂](ClO₄)₃; (6), (5) + 0.002 M H₃BO₃; initial vol. = 25 ml; titrant(NaOH) = 0.1M.

All the three *cis*-diaqua-cobalt complexes, [(N₄)Co(H₂O)₂]³⁺, N₄ = trien, (tn)₂ and (bipy)₂, show two well-defined buffer regions, the one in the pH range 4.5–6.5 and the other in the pH range 7.0–9.5. One mole of base per mole of the complexes is consumed in each of these buffer

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regions (curves 3, 5, Fig. 1), obviously due to successive deprotonation of the two coordinated H₂O ligands in these complexes³ according to

$$K^H(I) = ([II][H])/[I] \quad (2b)$$

$$K^H(II) = ([III][H])/[II] \quad (3b)$$

Charges are omitted for clarity. Two well-defined regions are also observed when 1 : 1 and 2 : 1 mixtures of these *cis*-[(N₄)Co(H₂O)₂]³⁺ complexes and H₃BO₃ are pH-metrically titrated with NaOH (curves 4, 6, Fig. 1). The first buffer region is superimposable with that of the first step deprotonation equilibria (2a) of these complexes and the amounts of base consumed in this buffer region (pH 4.5–6.5) are just equal to the molar concentrations of the complexes. The second buffer region occurs at pH values lower than that corresponding to the second step deprotonation equilibria (3a) of the complexes (curves 3, 5, Fig. 1) and also the ionisation equilibria (1) of H₃BO₃. The amounts of base consumed in this buffer region are exactly equal to the sum of the molar concentrations of the complexes and H₃BO₃.

It is, therefore, evident from these observations that the mono-aqua-mono-hydroxo complexes (II) resulting from deprotonation of the *cis*-diaqua complexes (I), having one OH group and one H₂O ligand in *cis*-positions are the actual species that react with H₃BO₃ to release proton at lower pH values in this second buffer region. As there is no chance of any ligand exchange reaction under the present experimental conditions, the mono-aqua-mono-hydroxo complexes (II) may react with H₃BO₃ according to equilibria (4a) and (5a) in the same manner as *cis*-1,2-diols react with H₃BO₃,

$$K^{2H}(H_3BO_3 + II) = ([IV][H]^2)/([II][H_3BO_3]) \quad (4b)$$

$$K^{3H}(H_3BO_3 + 2II) = ([V][H]^3)/([II]^2[H_3BO_3]) \quad (5b)$$

These reactions (4a and 5a) may be categorised as examples of pseudo-substitution⁴ in which Co^{III}-O bonds remain intact and the actual substitution of Co^{III}-bound OH moiety on the B(III) centre takes place with the release of H₃O⁺. The latter process being very fast, these equilibria are established rapidly. Mechanism of these reactions may be identical with those of the hydrolysis of carbonatopentaamminecobalt(III) complex into aquapentaamminecobalt(III)⁵ and conversion of the latter into nitrito-

pentaammine and bisulphitopentaammine analogues⁶. Tracer studies show no cleavage of Co-O bond in these interchanges, actual substitution takes place on the oxygen atom bound to Co^{III} and not on the metal centre itself. Tendency of B(III) cation to achieve tetracoordination through the formation of chelate complexes (IV) and (V) with the *cis*-aqua-hydroxo complexes (II) serves as the driving force to the reactions (4a and 5a).

The equilibrium constants : $K^H(H_3BO_3)$, $K^H(I)$, $K^H(II)$, $K^{2H}(H_3BO_3 + II)$, $K^{3H}(H_3BO_3 + 2II)$ are obtained as computer outputs from which the formation constants $\beta^H(IV)$ and $\beta^H(V)$ of the complexes (IV) and (V), respectively, defined according to (6) and (7),

$$\beta^H(IV) = ([IV][H])/([III][H_3BO_3]) \quad (6)$$

$$\beta^H(V) = ([V][H])/([III]^2[H_3BO_3]) \quad (7)$$

may be calculated using the relations (8) and (9),

$$\log \beta^H(IV) = \log K^{2H}(H_3BO_3 + II) - \log K^H(II) \quad (8)$$

$$\log \beta^H(V) = \log K^{3H}(H_3BO_3 + 2II) - 2 \log K^H(II) \quad (9)$$

Linear dependence of $\log \beta^H(IV)$ and $\log \beta^H(V)$ values upon $\log K^H(II)$ (Table 1) provides further evidence of complex formation of the mono-aqua-mono-hydroxo complexes (II) with H₃BO₃ as proposed according to equilibria (4a) and (5a). It is evident that higher the basicity of the coordinated OH groups in the *cis*-dihydroxocobalt complexes (III), stronger is the affinity of such OH groups to coordinate the electron deficient B(III) cation in H₃BO₃ and more stable are the mixed ligand Co^{III}-borate complexes (IV) and (V).

Table 1. Formation constants of *cis*-[(N₄)Co(H₂O)₂]³⁺-borate complexes in aqueous solution*

Parameter	(N ₄)				
	α -isomer	β -isomer	($\alpha + \beta$)eqlm. mix.	(tn) ₂	(bipy) ₂
$\log K^H(I)$	-5.54 (0.04)	-5.50 (0.05)	-5.52 (0.05)	-4.99 (0.06)	-4.19 (0.04)
$\log K^H(II)$	-7.93 (0.04)	-7.90 (0.06)	-7.92 (0.03)	-7.68 (0.04)	-6.77 (0.03)
$\log K^{2H}(H_3BO_3 + II)$	-5.73 (0.09)	-5.71 (0.16)	-5.71 (0.12)	-5.88 (0.11)	-5.87 (0.06)
$\log K^{3H}(H_3BO_3 + 2II)$	-2.71 (0.14)	-2.68 (0.18)	-2.71 (0.14)	-2.73 (0.17)	-2.99 (0.13)
$\log \beta^H(IV)$	2.20	2.22	2.21	1.80	0.90
$\log \beta^H(V)$	13.15	13.12	13.13	12.63	10.55

*Values in the parenthesis are standard deviations.

Among the *cis*-[(N₄)Co(H₂O)₂]³⁺ complexes chosen, *cis*-[(trien)Co(H₂O)₂]³⁺ may be obtained in two isomeric forms, viz. α -isomer (VI) and β -isomer (VII). The β -form

Fig. 2. Species distribution curves for (a) $[\text{Co}(\text{trien})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{3+} : \text{H}_3\text{BO}_3 = 1 : 1$; (b) $[\text{Co}(\text{trien})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{3+} : \text{H}_3\text{BO}_3 = 2 : 1$ systems : (1) $[\text{Co}(\text{trien})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{3+}$, (2) $[\text{Co}(\text{trien})(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{2+}$, (3) $[\text{Co}(\text{trien})(\text{OH})_2]^+$, (4) H_3BO_3 , (5) $\text{B}(\text{OH})_4^-$, (6) $[\text{Co}(\text{trien})(\text{H}_2\text{BO}_4)]^-$, (7) $[\text{Co}_2(\text{trien})_2(\text{BO}_4)]^+$.

Fig. 3. Species distribution curves for (a) $[\text{Co}(\text{tn})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{3+} : \text{H}_3\text{BO}_3 = 1 : 1$; (b) $[\text{Co}(\text{tn})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{3+} : \text{H}_3\text{BO}_3 = 2 : 1$ systems : (1) $[\text{Co}(\text{tn})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{3+}$, (2) $[\text{Co}(\text{tn})_2(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{2+}$, (3) $[\text{Co}(\text{tn})_2(\text{OH})_2]^+$, (4) H_3BO_3 , (5) $\text{B}(\text{OH})_4^-$, (6) $[\text{Co}(\text{tn})_2(\text{H}_2\text{BO}_4)]^-$, (7) $[\text{Co}_2(\text{tn})_4(\text{BO}_4)]^+$.

Fig. 4. Species distribution curves for (a) $[\text{Co}(\text{bipy})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{3+} : \text{H}_3\text{BO}_3 = 1 : 1$; (b) $[\text{Co}(\text{bipy})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{3+} : \text{H}_3\text{BO}_3 = 2 : 1$ system : (1) $[\text{Co}(\text{bipy})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{3+}$, (2) $[\text{Co}(\text{bipy})_2(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{2+}$, (3) $[\text{Co}(\text{bipy})_2(\text{OH})_2]^+$, (4) H_3BO_3 , (5) $\text{B}(\text{OH})_4^-$, (6) $[\text{Co}(\text{bipy})_2(\text{H}_2\text{BO}_4)]^-$, (7) $[\text{Co}_2(\text{bipy})_4(\text{BO}_4)]^+$.

is thermodynamically more stable than the α -analogue. The α -form spontaneously isomerises to an equilibrium mixture of 85% β and 15% α in solution⁷. Equilibrium study have been carried out separately with freshly prepared solutions of both the isomers and also with their equilibrium mixture (obtained on keeping the α -isomer in solution for a day) following the same experimental conditions. Identity of the results (within the limits of experimental errors) indicates that basicity of the OH groups bound to Co^{III} in these *cis*-dihydroxo complexes (III) is independent of any such geometrical factor.

Experimental

All the chemicals (A.R.) and their solutions were prepared in double-distilled CO_2 -free water. Boric acid (A.R.) was further purified by recrystallisation from hot water and air-dried. *cis*-Diaquacobalt(III) complexes, viz. *cis*- $[(\text{bipy})_2\text{Co}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and *cis*- $[(\text{tn})_2\text{Co}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_3 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were prepared from $\text{Na}_3[\text{Co}(\text{CO}_3)_3] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ⁸

following the reported procedures³. α - and β -isomers *cis*-[(trien)Co(H₂O)₂](ClO₄)₃ were prepared according to the procedure described in literature⁷. Purity of the complexes were checked by chemical analysis⁹ and spectral measurements^{3,7}. The absorption spectra of the *cis*-[(bipy)₂Co(H₂O)₂]³⁺ (λ_{max} 491 nm) and *cis*-[(tn)₂Co(H₂O)₂]³⁺ (λ_{max} 506 nm) complexes remained unchanged on keeping their aqueous solutions for several days at room temperature. However, the absorption spectra of α - and β -isomers of the *cis*-[(trien)Co(H₂O)₂]³⁺ complex which initially absorbed at λ_{max} 500 and 488 nm, respectively, became superimposable (λ_{max} 490 nm) on standing their solutions for ~24 h. This indicated that although the bipy and tn complexes were kinetically quite stable, the α - and β -isomers of the trien complex spontaneously transformed into an equilibrium mixture of 15% α - and 85% β -forms as reported⁷.

The following solutions, each of initial volume 25 ml and ionic strength, $I = 0.5 M$ (NaClO₄) were prepared for potentiometric measurements : (1), 0.002 *M* HClO₄; (2), (1) + 0.002 *M* H₃BO₃; (3), (1) + 0.002 *M* [(N₄)Co(H₂O)₂](ClO₄)₃; (4), (3) + 0.002 *M* H₃BO₃; (5), (1) + 0.004 *M* [(N₄)Co(H₂O)₂](ClO₄)₃; (6), (5) + 0.002 *M* H₃BO₃, where, N₄ = (trien), (tn)₂ and (bipy)₂. All the solutions were thermostated at 25° and titrated pH-metrically with carbonate-free standard 0.1 *M* NaOH solution¹⁰.

pH was measured with a Systronics 335 pH-meter employing a special glass electrode in conjunction with a SCE connected to the cell through a agar-2*M* NaNO₃ salt-bridge. Spectra were measured with a Hitachi U-3501 spectrophotometer. pK_w of water at the experimental temperature and activity coefficient of hydrogen ion at the experimental ionic strength were obtained from literature¹¹. Analytical concentrations of H⁺ ion at different pH meter readings were calculated according to usual procedure¹². Preliminary values of some of the binary equilibrium con-

stants were evaluated according to the method of Irving and Rossotti¹³. Final values of the formation constants were calculated with the aid of scogs programme¹⁴, run on a IBM 300GL personal computer. The constants were refined over several cycles of operation and the values corresponding to the minimum standard deviations were accepted. Complex formation equilibria were elucidated with the help of the speciation curves (Figs. 2-4).

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